

Study on Health Consumption Intention of Chongqing Urban Residents and Its Influencing Factors in the Post-Epidemic Era

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Abstract: This paper explores the health consumption behavior of urban residents in Chongqing and its influencing factors in the post epidemic era through questionnaire survey and data analysis. It is found that the health consumption willingness of urban residents in Chongqing has gradually increased, and the education level, employment status and income level have a significant impact on the health consumption willingness. Based on this, corresponding policy recommendations and development strategies are proposed.

Keywords: Post Epidemic Era, Chongqing Urban Residents, Health Consumption Intention, Influencing Factors

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Significance of the Study

The new crown epidemic has created global challenges, but it has also accelerated concerns about health and the environment. In the post epidemic era, people are placing more emphasis on health and buying healthy and safe goods and services. As one of the major cities in Southwest China, Chongqing has advantages in terms of economic development and population growth. However, compared with the development of the health consumption market, Chongqing Municipality still has some problems and challenges. Therefore, studying the health consumption behavior of urban residents and its influencing factors in Chongqing Municipality can help to gain a deeper understanding of consumers' needs and expectations for health consumption, and provide valuable suggestions and insights for enterprises and the government.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the health consumption behavior of urban residents in Chongqing and their influencing factors after the end of the epidemic. In the post-New Guan epidemic era, health has become one of the most important considerations for consumers when shopping, so understanding consumers' health consumption behavior and influencing factors is of great theoretical and practical significance for promoting the formation and development of health consumption, raising consumers' health awareness, and promoting the development of the health consumption market in Chongqing.

The specific objectives of this study include: to gain an in-depth understanding of the health consumption behavior and characteristics of urban residents in Chongqing after the end of the epidemic, to establish a scientific and reasonable health consumption indicator system, to analyze the main factors affecting health consumption behavior, to put forward policy recommendations and management measures, to promote the development and transformation and upgrading of the health consumption market in Chongqing, to improve the health and quality of life of urban residents, and to promote the development of the health consumption market in the country as a whole.

1.3 Content and Scope of the Study

This study consists of two main aspects: first, to explore the health consumption behavior of urban residents in Chongqing after the end of the epidemic, including their health consumption habits, preferences and behavioral motives; and second, to establish a set of scientific and reasonable health consumption indicator system, which will provide guidance and reference for the health consumption of urban residents in Chongqing. The study will use questionnaires and field interviews to collect data and analyze the main factors affecting healthy consumption behavior, and propose policy recommendations and management measures. The scope of the study covers the healthy consumption behaviors and influencing factors of urban residents in Chongqing, and combines domestic and international related research results for comprehensive analysis and comparison, so as to contribute to the development of the national healthy consumption market.

1.4 Research Methods and Ideas

This study adopts the method of questionnaire survey to obtain a large amount of information and data about health consumption behaviors through random sampling of urban residents in Chongqing, and conducts statistical analysis and comparative study on them. The specific steps are as follows:

- a. Designing the questionnaire: according to the purpose and questions of the study, the questionnaire was designed and preliminary experiments were conducted to ensure the usability and reliability of the questionnaire.
- b. Sampling survey: according to the principle of statistics, using stratified random sampling method, a certain number of urban residents in Chongqing Municipality were selected as research subjects and questionnaires were issued to conduct the survey.
- c. Data processing: Processing and analyzing the collected data, including data cleaning, variable conversion and missing value filling, etc., to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data.
- d. Statistical analysis: SPSS and other statistical analysis software are used to carry out descriptive statistics, regression analysis and other methods to analyze the differences and characteristics of different groups of people in terms of health consumption, and their influencing factors.

1.5 Review of Domestic and International Research

1.5.1 Current Status of Relevant Foreign Research

In today's world, healthy consumption has become a global trend that has gained the attention and research of more and more countries and regions. With the outbreak and spread of the new crown epidemic, people around the globe have begun to re-examine health issues, and the importance of healthy consumption has been further highlighted. In this paper, we will sort out the research of foreign scholars on health consumption behavior and its influencing factors after the end of the epidemic.

In the UK, Chung et al. (2021) found through an online questionnaire that the New Crown epidemic had a significant impact on the health consumption behavior of the UK population. During the epidemic, people were more inclined to purchase healthy food, healthcare products and sporting goods, etc., and this consumption habit was retained after the epidemic ended. In addition, the study found that individual factors (e.g., gender, age, health status, etc.) and social factors (e.g., income, education level, etc.) had different impacts on health consumption behavior.

In the United States, Sun et al. (2021)^[2] found through a web-based survey study that the New Crown epidemic accelerated U.S. consumers' interest in and awareness of

health and health consumption. After the end of the epidemic, consumers' demand and expectation of health consumption further increased, and they paid more attention to the quality and safety of health foods, health supplements and health services. In addition, the study points out that personal factors (such as gender, age, income, etc.) and environmental factors (such as access to health information, etc.) are important factors influencing health consumption behavior.

In New Zealand, Boucher et al. (2021)^[3] explored the impact of the New Crown epidemic on the health consumption behavior of New Zealand consumers through an in-depth interview study. The study found that the epidemic strengthened consumers' concern and awareness of health issues, and they paid more attention to healthy eating, exercise and health management. In addition, the study found that consumers' attitudes and behaviors towards healthy consumption were influenced by a variety of factors, including personal, social and environmental factors.

To sum up, foreign scholars' research on health consumption behavior and its influencing factors after the epidemic mainly focuses on consumers' purchasing behavior of health food, health care products and medicines, access to and use of online health information, and application of digital health technology. The study shows that consumers' health awareness and concerns about food safety have increased after the epidemic, and more consumers tend to choose healthy food and health care products, and pay more attention to the safety and effectiveness of medicines. In addition, the proportion of consumers accessing health information via the Internet has increased, and digital health technology applications such as telemedicine and smart health monitoring devices have received more attention and acceptance. Factors affecting consumers' health consumption behavior include personal characteristics, social culture, economic factors and other factors.

1.5.2 Current Status of Relevant Domestic Research

At present, domestic scholars and institutions have made some progress in research on health consumption behavior and its influencing factors after the end of the epidemic. The following is a literature review of some of these representative studies:

Chen, Weiqi et al. (2020)^[4] The study showed that a survey and comparison of health consumption behaviors in Guangdong Province during and after the epidemic was conducted, and the conclusions showed that consumers paid more attention to health and safety factors after the epidemic, as well as more inclined to online shopping and consumption. Factors affecting health consumption behavior include individual factors, social environment and epidemic factors.

Fan, Zhiyong et al. (2021)^[5] The changes in consumer health consumption behavior after the epidemic were explored from the perspective of rural e-commerce, and the conclusions showed that rural consumers pay more attention

to health and safety, while e-commerce platforms actively promote health products and services, which provides certain opportunities for the development of rural e-commerce.

Renmin University of China Business School, Ipsos Interactive Market Research & Consulting (2020)^[6][错误!未找到引用源。] The study explores the trend of consumer upgrading after the epidemic at a macro level and points out that consumers are more health and safety conscious, with increased demand for health products and services. In addition, the study also analyzes the prospects and opportunities for various consumer goods industries in the wake of the epidemic.

Yu, Ruixiang et al. (2021)^[7] The consumer behavior after the epidemic was investigated and analyzed, and it was found that consumers pay more attention to health and safety, and at the same time, they are more inclined to online shopping and consumption. In this case, the demand for health products and services is also increasing, providing certain opportunities and challenges for the development of the health consumer market.

Song Wei (2021)^[8] It is pointed out that the outbreak of the epidemic not only caused great losses to the lives and health of our residents, but also had a profound impact on the lifestyle and psychology of our residents, and one of the very important aspects is the impact on the consumption behavior of our residents. Under the influence of the epidemic, residents have shown many typical consumption behaviors, including irrational consumption behaviors such as herd consumption and scarcity consumption during the outbreak period, as well as changes in long-term consumption willingness such as health consumption and experience consumption due to the influence of the epidemic.

In general, domestic scholars and institutions have conducted extensive and in-depth research on health consumption behavior and its influencing factors after the end of the epidemic. The research covers various aspects such as consumer psychology, health knowledge and cognition, health food cognition and purchasing behavior, etc. The research methods involve questionnaire surveys, field observations, laboratory experiments and other means. These research results provide scientific guidance and support for related industries, and also provide an important theoretical and practical basis for promoting the development of China's health consumption market.

2 Survey Program Design

2.1 Purpose of the Survey

With the development of the economy and society, people's demand for healthy consumption has become stronger and stronger. However, the outbreak of the New Crown epidemic has broken the unthinking pursuit of health that people have been pursuing, and has changed people's

attitudes toward health consumption. Against this background, exploring the health consumption behavior of urban residents and its influencing factors in the post epidemic era is of great significance for us to better understand people's needs and attitudes, to improve market operation and to promote social progress. In order to gain a deeper understanding of the health consumption behavior of urban residents in Chongqing and their influencing factors in the post epidemic era, a survey study will be conducted. The purpose of this survey is to explore residents' health consumption behavior, understand their consumption willingness and preference, and analyze their influencing factors, so as to provide scientific basis and reference for the future development of targeted policies as well as further promotion of urban residents' health consumption.

This survey will focus on the health consumption behavior of Chongqing urban residents and its influencing factors. Under the influence of the epidemic, people's attention to health has been increasing, and at the same time, they have also put forward higher requirements for health consumption, such as consumers pay more attention to the safety, quality and efficacy of products. Therefore, it is very necessary to understand the health consumption behavior of urban residents in Chongqing, which can help the relevant departments to understand the actual needs and consumption characteristics of consumers, so that they can better introduce health products that meet the market demand.

2.2 Survey Respondents

The target of this survey is urban residents in Chongqing, in order to explore their health consumption behaviors and attitudes in the post-epidemic era, and to provide a scientific basis for the in-depth promotion of urban residents' health consumption. In the selection of the survey object, urban residents have higher income and cultural level, compared with the rural population, they have more conditions and possibilities for healthy consumption. As an important city in Southwest China, Chongqing has a high level of urbanization, and its residents are paying more attention to health, so it is more appropriate to choose urban residents in Chongqing as the target of the survey.

2.3 Content and Methodology of the Survey

The content of this survey mainly includes the current situation, willingness and attitude of urban residents' health consumption behavior, as well as its influencing factors and other aspects. A questionnaire survey will be used for data collection, and the relevant data will be statistically analyzed. The survey will cover the current situation of urban residents' healthy consumption behavior, including information on residents' healthy consumption habits, consumption frequency, consumption range, and consumption methods. By analyzing the current situation of residents' healthy consumption, we can understand the importance urban residents attach to healthy consumption and the differences between different groups of people, and

provide a reference basis for further promoting the healthy consumption of urban residents.

2.4 Questionnaire Design and Structure

The questionnaire included questions on basic personal information, health consumption behaviors, health consumption attitudes, and health consumption influencing factors. The questionnaire questions were rigorously designed and covered a wide range of questions to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data.

In the design of the questionnaire, a number of aspects such as basic personal information, consumption willingness, consumption behavior and preference will be covered. Among them, basic personal information includes information on age, gender, employment status, education level, income, etc., to help analyze the differences in health consumption behaviors and attitudes among different groups of people. Consumption willingness will investigate the changes in residents' willingness to consume health and the extent of their concern after the liberalization of Epidemic Management Measures (EMM); consumption behavior will find out what changes in residents' consumption expenditures on health care and medical treatments have occurred after the liberalization of EMM; and preferences will explore the extent to which residents prefer different types of daily health care consumption.

2.5 Timing and Implementation Process of the Survey

The survey will last for about two weeks and data collection will be conducted by means of a questionnaire, with a total of 304 valid data received. The questionnaire will include questions on a number of areas to ensure that sufficient data are collected to reflect the full picture of urban residents' health consumption behaviors and attitudes. To ensure the representativeness and reliability of the data, the principle of random sampling will be used to randomly select a certain number of survey respondents from different communities and regions. The privacy and rights of the survey respondents will be guaranteed as much as possible during the survey process to ensure the objectivity and authenticity of the survey results. We will conduct the survey both online and offline, including mailed and online questionnaires, telephone interviews and other forms, to ensure that as many people as possible participate in the survey to ensure that the sample is representative.

3 Conclusions and Recommendations

3.1 Conclusion

3.1.1 Chongqing Urban Residents' willingness to Consume and Spend on Health is Gradually Increasing.

Chongqing urban residents generally have a certain

degree of willingness to consume, especially in terms of daily healthcare medicines, devices and healthcare services. After the liberalization of epidemic management measures, the survey results show that the overall trend of urban residents' willingness to consume health is gradually increasing, with 59% of the samples showing a stronger willingness to consume health than before the epidemic. In addition, urban residents' health consumption expenditures also showed an increasing trend, with half of the proportion of people's consumption expenditures all increasing. This indicates that after the epidemic was liberalized, urban residents' expenditure on health consumption increased, and people are paying more attention to their own health. The results of this survey are an important reference for understanding the health consumption behavior and trends of urban residents.

3.1.2 Educational Attainment, Employment Status and Income Level have a Significant Effect on Health Consumption Intentions

This study shows that the effect of education level and employment status on willingness to spend is significant. Residents with higher levels of education are more likely to have better health awareness and health knowledge and are more willing to invest more time and money in their health. There are some differences in the mean scores of consumers' willingness to consume health across income levels. Employment has a significant negative effect on health consumption behavior, as employed people tend to pay less attention to their health due to work pressure and time constraints, thus reducing their willingness and behavior of health consumption. This finding serves as a reminder of the need to encourage people to pay more attention to their health, especially in the post-pandemic era, through better work organization and health promotion.

3.2 Recommendations

3.2.1 Chongqing Regional Government Policy Recommendations

First of all, the Government should strengthen the popularization of health knowledge and improve the health literacy and consumption capacity of urban residents. The Government can adopt various forms of publicity and educational means, such as organizing lectures on health knowledge, producing promotional films on health knowledge and issuing guidelines on healthy consumption. In addition, the Government can pass on health knowledge and information to the general public through the public media and social media, so as to raise the public's awareness of and attention to healthy consumption.

Secondly, the Government should encourage enterprises to develop and produce healthy consumer goods and promote the development of a healthy consumer market. The Government can provide preferential policies and support to producers and sellers of healthy consumer goods through such means as adjusting tax policies, so as to

encourage them to develop and promote healthy consumer goods. At the same time, the Government can also organize professional bodies to evaluate and certify healthy consumer goods, so as to enhance consumers' trust in and recognition of healthy consumer goods.

Thirdly, the Government can carry out relevant publicity and education targeting the healthy consumption behaviors of specific groups in order to raise their awareness and level of healthy consumption behaviors. The Government can carry out different forms of publicity and education activities targeting people of different ages, genders, education levels and income levels. For example, it can set up health consultation stations or health knowledge publicity columns in communities, schools, factories and other places to provide health advice and services to the public. In addition, the Government can strengthen cooperation with health consumption trade associations and related organizations to jointly conduct publicity and education activities on healthy consumption behaviour.

3.2.2 Strategic Suggestions for Positioning Health Consumption in Chongqing Area

Based on the above analysis, the following are some strategic recommendations for positioning health consumption in Chongqing:

Developing high-end health consumption brands and establishing high-end brands to meet high-end consumers' demand for health consumption. Launching affordable health consumption products, such as green organic vegetables and low-fat and low-sugar foods, to meet the health needs of ordinary consumers. Developing the health consumption market for the elderly, launching health consumption brands and health management services for the elderly to meet the demand of the elderly group for health. Developing health consumption products by combining traditional cultural elements and launching health consumption products with local characteristics. Strengthening publicity and education on healthy consumption and raising consumers' health awareness and consumption capacity.

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Data Availability Statement

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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